

Mapping potential soil water repellency in Denmark

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What is soil water repellency ?

Understanding the mechanisms of soil water repellency from nanoscale to ecosystem scale: a review

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Why is soil water repellency important ?

Why is soil water repellency important ?

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Plant and soil communities are associated with the response of soil water repellency to environmental stress

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Mapping soil water repellency (SWR) in Denmark

1. National SWR survey across habitats, land uses and soil types
2. Map SWR at national scale
3. Identify the main drivers of SWR

Mapping soil water repellency in Denmark

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- Soil water repellency samples (~7600)
 - Quantile Random Forest model (q0.10, q0.50, q0.90)
 - Covariates at 10m resolution (Soil, vegetation and landscape attributes)

Soil water repellency samples

oil water repellency samples

Map of soil water repellency

(a)

(b)

(c)

Habitats x Soil

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